

Skills Assessment Questionnaire - ATRIUM

This questionnaire has been developed as part of task 7.1 within the [ATRIUM project](#), funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement n. 101132163. The aim is to assess the skills (knowledge, abilities, and competencies) required for the active use of services/software provided by ATRIUM research infrastructures and partners, namely those listed in the [ATRIUM Portfolio](#).

You received this link because you were identified as the contact point for one or more of the services/software of the ATRIUM Portfolio. Please note that each service/software requires an individual response to this questionnaire. If you have any questions, please contact Carol Delmazo, task 7.1 leader: carol.delmazo@operas-eu.org.

Deadline to complete the questionnaire: 14/06/2024.

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

Contact point

The information requested in this section will not be made publicly available. It will be used **only internally within the ATRIUM project** and just for contact purposes, in case we need to clarify doubts or gather more information about the service.

For more information concerning data processing, please click here: [7.1 Questionnaire-Information on Data Processing and Declaration of Consent-ATRIUM.pdf \(atrium-research.eu\)](#).

2. **Contact point: name ***

3. **Contact point: email ***

4. **Contact point: institution ***

Service/software details

5. **1. Service/software name ***

⌵ Dropdown

Mark only one oval.

- 3DHOP
- AMCR Digital Archive
- Annotorious
- Multilingual NLP for Archaeological Reports Ariadne Infrastructure
- ARCHE
- 3M - Mapping Memory Manager
- ARIADNE Data Management Plan - Tool and Template
- ARIADNE EpHEMERA
- ARIADNE Lab VRE
- ARIADNE Linked Open Data
- **CANCELLED**
- ARIADNE portal
- ARIADNE Visual Media Service
- ARIADNE Vocabulary Matching Tool
- Virtual Language Observatory
- CLST Language and Speech Tools
- DARIAH-Campus
- Datasheet Editor
- Dendrochronology Entity Recognizer (English, Dutch, Swedish)
- Digital Repository of Scientific Institutes
- Transformations: A DARIAH Journal
- eScriptorium
- FBC
- GATE
- GATE Cloud
- GeoBrowser
- GoTriple
- Grobid

- Journals of the Polish Academy of Sciences
- LINDAT Translation
- Marian NMT
- OPERAS Metrics
- NameTag
- NEXUS
- OCR4all
- OpenLIME
- PERO OCR
- Recogito
- Research Spotlight
- SSH Open Marketplace
- SSH Vocabulary Commons
- Language Resource Switchboard
- TEITOK
- Tesseract
- UDPipe
- Virtual Transcription Laboratory
- Vocabs services
- X3ML Engine

6. **2. Please provide a brief description of the service/software ***

7. **3. When was the service/software first released (year)?* ***

8. **4. Who are the targeted users? (Please check all that apply) ***

Check all that apply.

- Citizen scientists
- Data creators
- Data engineers
- Data providers
- Data stewards
- Private sector and industry
- Public
- Publishers
- Repositories
- Research funders and policy makers
- Research libraries
- Research support
- Researchers
- Service providers
- Students
- Trainers
- Other: _____

9. **5. In case the service/software processes language, which languages does it support?**

10. **6. Which discipline(s) is the service/software targeting? ***

Check all that apply.

- Social Sciences disciplines
- Humanities disciplines
- Arts disciplines
- Specific for Archaeology
- Other: _____

11. **7. What are the needs of the target users that the service/software is expected to meet? ***

12. **8. Which previous knowledge (theoretical background) and/or practical skills (e.g. the use of GitHub, basic NLP skills) are required for the active use of the service/software? In case of software, what are the steps needed to run it? (download, local installation) ***

13. **9. How do you gather feedback from the users? ***

Check all that apply.

- Conducting surveys
- Searching through user forums
- Feedback forms at the end of a training/workshop about the service
- GitHub issues
- Other: _____

14. **10. How do you provide help/assistance when users face difficulties using the service/software? ***

Check all that apply.

- E-mail
- Mailing list
- Helpdesk
- User forum
- GitHub (e.g. users can submit tickets for bugs or new feature requests)
- Other: _____

15. **11. Are you providing training for this service/software? If yes, please describe it in as much detail as possible: type of training, materials available (if they are online), language(s)...** *

16. **12. Are there any training topics/resources/formats that you think ^{*} would be useful to improve the use of the service/software and could be included in the ATRIUM Curriculum*?**

**The insights from this Skills Assessment will contribute to what we call the "ATRIUM Curriculum", an integrated and comprehensive set of courses that will be hosted, maintained and sustained on DARIAH-Campus.*

17. **13. Are you aware of any access gap^{*} or restrictions in the use of ^{*} the service/software?**

**We are trying to understand if there is an access gap, e.g. if the service/software is more accessed in some countries than in others, or accessed by some specific communities more than others, or if there are access restrictions (log in to the university account, the user interface language...)*

18. **14. How far does the service/software adhere to guidelines that make it more accessible to a wider range of people with disabilities?** *

[Web Content Accessibility Guidelines \(WCAG\) 2.1 \(w3.org\)](https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/wcag/)

19. **15. Is there anything else you would like to say concerning the use of the service/software?**

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